

DEMYSTIFYING THE STORIES OF TEACHERS TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION TO SPECIAL CHILDREN: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 2

Pages: 179-188

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2749

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14614927

Manuscript Accepted: 11-25-2024

Demystifying The Stories of Teachers Teaching Physical Education to Special Children: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

A The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating six cooperating teachers from one public schools in Davao region were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interview. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: encouraging both challenges and joy in sharing knowledge and experience; dealing with pedagogical challenges instructing on the formulation of lesson plans; handling behaviors typical into special children; and providing support from parents and co-workers in improving classroom management skills due to their lack of experience. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: balancing and managing time; practicing open communication and behavior of students; consulting with colleagues for advice; and processing parents' and co-teachers' self-reflection for guidance. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: inspire passion and commitment to the teaching profession; encourage continuous learning and personal development in teaching; consistently uphold diligence in dedication to teaching; and be role models. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, passion and commitment teachers, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

Teachers encounter several challenges when working with children with learning disabilities, including issues related to teaching materials and curriculum structure, behavioral problems, time constraints, and parental expectations and involvement. Additional difficulties include motivation, self-esteem, and emotional concerns. Specific challenges noted include communication difficulties, parental denial about their children's conditions, delayed motor skills, insufficient parental support, and ongoing behavioral issues. However, through the educational practices implemented by teachers tailored to meet these children's needs, several positive outcomes have emerged. These include enhanced participation in various activities, improved verbal and non-verbal communication skills, better behavior through straightforward instructions, increased social interaction with peers, and advancements in reading and writing abilities (Ahammed, 2021; Catoto, 2023).

In Zimbabwe, the concept of inclusive education has largely been shaped by perspectives from the global north, often overlooking the challenges faced by schools in lower-income countries with limited resources. These schools may lack the necessary infrastructure to support inclusivity. Teachers, grappling with low salaries, diminishing motivation, insufficient teaching materials, deteriorating facilities, overcrowded classrooms, and students struggling to pay fees, may not prioritize inclusive education. Even those educators who understand and value its principles find it difficult to implement them amid these daily challenges (Mutanga, 2023).

In the Philippines, a study conducted by a special education (SPED) teacher in the City Division of Ilagan Isabela highlighted several challenges faced by teachers working with children who have learning disabilities. The research identified five main themes: the need to choose suitable teaching strategies and foster motivation, the importance of recognizing each student's unique needs, the challenges and rewards inherent in teaching, the necessity of acceptance and patience, and the significance of respecting students' rights. The teachers working with children with learning disabilities reported that they had not received any formal training in special needs education, which left them feeling unqualified. Moreover, teachers in SPED classes frequently struggle to implement effective strategies tailored to the needs of learners with disabilities. The study revealed that classrooms for children with learning disabilities in the Ilagan division are hindered by poor learning environments, including limited budgets, a lack of curriculum guides, insufficient instructional materials, and inadequate facilities. It concluded that merely placing learners with special needs in inclusive classrooms alongside their peers is not enough without proper support. These students often lack the essential services and resources needed to engage with the curriculum, and support from stakeholders for those in SPED programs remains minimal (Allam et al., 2021).

This study holds significant social relevance as it highlights how teaching Physical Education equips students with essential knowledge and skills for interacting with others, while also providing opportunities to develop these competencies. It fosters leadership and teamwork abilities and encourages students to apply their knowledge across different subjects. However, the study also requires urgent research attention due to teacher-related factors, such as perceived competence and experience in teaching students with disabilities, as well as the academic coursework in special education or inclusive Physical Education. Teachers of Physical Education are more inclined to positively engage with students with disabilities if they have received advanced training in Adapted Physical Education (APE) and possess greater experience in working with these students.

In my literature review, I found related studies, including Aldagamseh et al. (2023), which examined the attitudes of Physical Education

teachers toward the inclusion of students with disabilities in PE classes, and Macharty et al. (2022), which explored whether experience with students with disabilities better equips teachers for inclusive practices. These studies investigate how early, authentic experiences working with children with disabilities in specialized school environments influence participants' development of inclusive skills, their confidence in working with these students, and the optimal duration of contact needed to foster confidence in teaching in inclusive settings.

Upon the completion of this study, dissemination efforts would be done to encourage the readers and members of the academic community to disseminate further and utilize the findings of this study. A free copy of the study would be given to the schools where the study would be conducted. Further, I would guarantee the publication of this study in a reputable and refereed journal to encourage further the dissemination of this study.

Research Questions

The observational study targeted the teachers teaching physical education to special children. Therefore, the important questions that were tackled are as follows:

1. What are the teacher's experiences in teaching physical education to special children?
2. How do teachers cope with the difficulties they encounter when instructing students with learning disabilities, and how do they get past them?
3. What are the insights that will be used in teaching approaches and methodology to special children?

Literature Review

Special Children

Special education requires teachers to collaborate closely with various stakeholders, including general education teachers, parents, school administrators, and others. This makes the ability to understand others and think critically essential. Additionally, special education teachers often experience emotional stress due to heavy workloads and the slow progress of students with disabilities (Fu et al., 2019). Children with disabilities and special needs in inclusive settings are less likely to experience limited academic opportunities and be negatively affected in their future academic opportunities, compared to those in self-contained special education classrooms (Parekh et al., 2019).

The importance of an aspiring teacher's ability to pause and reflect during challenging situations is highlighted by the concept of "reflection-in-action." This involves considering all experiences—both tactical and intellectual—as they occur in real time. If this practical knowledge remains unarticulated, there is a risk that prospective teachers may not fully utilize their potential in their future roles, especially within the context of inclusive education practices (Schön, 2023).

In addition, educational techniques that emphasize the teacher's ongoing emotional interaction with children are crucial. Traditional methods enrich children's imagination, fostering numerous associations with their social and emotional experiences while also promoting speech development. These techniques help enhance students' individual talents and their understanding of professional and social self-identification (Berehova, 2019).

Adapted Physical Education

Physical education is a course aimed at enhancing students' physical health and well-being. In this class, students engage in a variety of activities, including team sports, individual sports, dance, and fitness exercises. Research indicates that physical education is a vital component of a student's overall education, as it promotes health, fosters teamwork skills, and provides an enjoyable experience. Additionally, physical education supports students in maintaining a healthy weight and lowering the risk of obesity (Llego, 2023).

Teachers aim for their students to reach their fullest potential and are continually seeking effective strategies to support their learning. Our findings highlight the significance of a student's academic self-concept in shaping engagement patterns, indicating that higher engagement is associated with greater academic achievement (Schnitzler et al., 2020).

A physical education teacher must create an environment conducive to holistic development, addressing both the physical and emotional aspects of students, where values are formed and instilled. It's important to teach the significance of discipline and focus. Students may be familiar with these concepts, they often fail to apply them. In PE, the importance of self-control and dedication should be emphasized so that students can incorporate these qualities into their everyday lives. Whether in sports or music, there should be a commitment to striving for excellence, even if it requires making lifestyle adjustments (Pangalangan, 2018).

Inclusive Education

The effectiveness of inclusive education heavily relies on teacher competencies such as collaboration, empathy, strong communication, and active listening to address diverse needs. Among these competencies, emotional intelligence is particularly crucial (Skura et al., 2022). In collaborative learning environments, where students of different abilities work together on projects, a spirit of mutual support develops. For instance, our friend who is mute and deaf not only received assistance but also inspired others with her resilience and

determination, leaving a lasting impact on her peers (Ronolo, 2024).

The learners with dissimilar traits due to psychological, behavioral, social, academic, and physical differences create challenges for many educators (Moore, et, al. 2018). Teachers struggle to provide stimulating academic support for some students in inclusion classrooms (Chitiyo et al.,2018).

Social and Emotional Well-being

The literature emphasizes the pivotal role of nurturing the social and emotional well-being of special children in physical education. Successful stories highlight teachers prioritizing positive peer environments, fostering friendships, and instilling a sense of belonging, leading to improved adapted behavior, enhanced relationships, better academics, healthier coping mechanisms, and elevated leadership skills (Kaur, 2022).

The continuous training model for teachers' professional development emphasizes their practices and experiences, linking them to meaningful contexts while highlighting the importance of social and emotional competencies to enhance teachers' effectiveness and professional growth. Reflective teaching involves educators Thus, prioritizing student well-being is crucial, requiring understanding from both teachers and school administrators. Teachers' instructional approaches should emphasize student well-being rather than just focusing on delivering learning materials. Promoting student well-being serves as a motivational force in the learning process, enhancing the overall educational experience and serving as a key indicator of school development (Nurhayana, 2020).

Furthermore, ongoing efforts to improve teaching skills are vital for sustaining student well-being. Teachers are crucial in creating a supportive learning atmosphere, and at the elementary level, they must enhance their teaching skills and incorporate digital methodologies, particularly through a variety of digital educational games (Tärning et al., 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a multiple case study approach, aiming to identify the challenges teachers encounter in inclusive classrooms and the strategies they use to address them. A descriptive research design was utilized to gather information from special needs education teachers, focusing on the specific research problem at hand. Since descriptive research aimed to understand the current state of a field, this approach was well-suited for collecting essential insights into the challenges faced by teachers working with learners with developmental disabilities and their methods for overcoming these obstacles. This design significantly enhanced understanding of the difficulties teachers faced, highlighting the need for targeted support and resources (Allam, 2021).

The study took place at Maniki Central Elementary School - SPED Center, focusing on selected teachers who provided physical education to students with special needs. The respondents were chosen using a multiple case study approach, primarily targeting regular teachers. It was determined that special needs teachers with extensive experience working with students with disabilities would be ideal for addressing the research questions. Inclusion allowed students with disabilities to spend more time with their peers, positively influencing regular students by fostering understanding and awareness of their classmates, who were integral members of society. This interaction not only enhanced social cohesion but also enriches the educational experience for all students involved (Bavli et al., 2020).

Participants

This study used a multiple case study. The main objective was to know the stories faced by teachers when teaching with special children and how they tried to overcome them. Therefore, one criterion of choosing participants was based on the fact that only special needs education teachers were wanted for the interview. The participants were selected based on the following criteria: (i) an elementary teacher (ii) a teacher who has experiences in teaching physical education to special children and (iii) employed teacher in Maniki Central Elementary School SPED Center. To determine the issues and challenges of teachers in teaching physical education to special children.

The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with three (3) cases and in each case, it had a two participats, and did a one-on-one interview with each of the participant. The researcher meticulously selected six (6) teachers in Maniki Central Elementary School - SPED Center in the province of Davao del Norte.

Procedure

Data collection is a vital stage in the research process, requiring meticulous planning and execution to obtain high-quality data. Employing scientific methodological rigor is essential to guarantee that the study yields reliable and valid results. This diligence not only enhances the credibility of the findings but also ensures that the research can effectively inform practice and policy (Hazari, 2024).

Firstly, prior to conducting the study, an approval letter from the Maniki Central Elementary School SPED Center. Obtained and noted by the research consultant. A guide questionnaire was employed. The interview question was presented first to the panel of examiners for approval to be able to proceed to the next step of data collection.

Secondly, after approval, information about the study's significance, purpose, and goals was provided to participants and individuals.

Depending on which language the participants spoke best, each question on the interview guide was translated. In addition, participants could respond to the questions in whichever language they felt most at ease.

Thirdly, an informed consent form detailing the participants' voluntary participation in the study was given to them to sign. Next, it is critical for the researcher to explain to the participants how their privacy will be protected. This means that the information was only used for the study. For the conduct of in-depth interviews schedule was established.

Moreover, the researcher also introduced the participants before the interview began. The researcher expressed my gratitude for their time and willingness to speak up. The researcher then explained the aim and scope of the study and informed the participants that the interview had been screen recorded, though their faces had been blurred to protect their identities.

In addition, the researcher prepared questions in advance of the scheduled time for the in-depth interview, and these questions were approved by the panelist. The researcher separately conducted our multiple case study Case one: Trisomy 21, Case two: Cerebral Palsy, Case three: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). It was noted to ask for their consent and permission before starting to record the interviews. Then, the researcher started to glean the experiences of the participants. Each question on the interview guide was translated into any language that the participants understood best. Furthermore, the questions were answered in Bisaya, tagalog, and English the participant was most comfortable with.

Consequently, the data was first converted from the original language to Standard English by the researcher after it had been recorded. The research was conducted after the data had been translated, and using the thematic analysis tenets, the researcher extracted the emerging themes. Finally, the themes that had been extracted were given to a data analyst whose knowledge of language research was compatible for approval and verification (Creswell, 2013). From the data transcription, the participants and informants were called to sign their certificates of completion as the participants of the study. Lastly, as a sign of thanks, tokens were given to the participants who wholeheartedly expressed their feelings and emotions, as well as their valued time and efforts in this study.

Data Analysis

Data analysis about the Demystifying the stories of teachers teaching physical education to special children. Research shows that inclusive physical education programs, which include students with disabilities in regular physical education classes, have been increasing in recent years. However, there is still work to be done as many schools have separate physical education classes or limited participation for students with disabilities. Physical education teachers often lack specific training in adapting curriculum and activities for students with disabilities. This can result in a lack of knowledge and confidence in providing inclusive physical education instruction.

In this study, the gathered data in this research was displayed and analyzed based on the needs and objectives of this research endeavor. In addition, the interviews of participants would be transcribed, and essential quotes would be highlighted. Researchers went over each study participant's data to obtain a feel of the overall picture, writing notes and codes in the margins to identify potentially significant markers of the appence. This process is called "horizontalization" in the assumption that all components of a description are related to one another and that understanding the relationship between the parts requires reading the complete description at least once.

Data analysis is inherently subjective and involves rich, detailed information typically conveyed through qualitative means. It encompasses non-numeric data such as interview transcripts, notes, audio and video recordings, photographs, and text documents. The aim of this process is to assist the researcher in collecting insights that enhance public understanding of the multiple case study or research topic (Pedamkar, 2023). By thoroughly analyzing this qualitative data, researchers can uncover deeper themes and patterns that contribute to a more nuanced perspective on the subject matter. In addition, Transcripts of selected teachers' IDI have become the primary source of data analysis. The data has been subjected to a number of treatments and processes in order to obtain the study's conclusions. Finally, researchers examine the transformed meaning units for patterns and important aspects that have been synthesized into a literary experience structure. Other than that, The data was analyzed using data reduction.

Ethical Considerations

The primary goal of this study is to guarantee the security, complete protection, and establishment of assurance of the informants. As a result, I made sure they were safe and gave them my full protection so they would not lose faith in me. Hence, I also complied with the following ethical standards when conducting his research: respect for people, goodness, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Boyatzis et al., 1998).

The attitudes and awareness of teachers, administrators, and peers play a crucial role in shaping the experiences of students with disabilities in physical education. Negative perceptions, misconceptions, and stereotypes can lead to exclusion or reduced opportunities for these students. Additionally, concerns about safety in physical education settings may emerge regarding students with disabilities. It is essential for teachers to possess a thorough understanding of various conditions and disabilities to effectively address any safety issues. Before conducting interviews, the researcher sought permission from the participants and adjusted the schedule according to their availability. This proactive approach ensured that the researcher would not disrupt the participants' classes or important commitments, facilitating a smooth interview process. Establishing this considerate schedule also aimed to foster a more relaxed environment for open dialogue. In conducting my study, I developed a friendly relationship with my participants. Prior to recording

our conversation, I sought their approval. Through face-to-face interview, I used this during our IDI. Other than that, I allowed them to ask questions before, during, or after the interviews were conducted. More importantly, I persisted in keeping all IDI proceedings strictly confidential from the public.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion section presents findings derived from a qualitative approach aimed at exploring the unique perspectives, experiences, and insights of teachers working in physical education with students with disabilities. This study employed a multiple case study design, focusing on three distinct cases: a teacher instructing students with Trisomy 21, another working with students with cerebral palsy, and a third teaching students with autism spectrum disorder. By centering on the lived experiences of these educators, the analysis uncovers valuable insights into the specific challenges, strategies, and adaptive practices employed in special education physical instruction. This approach enables a nuanced understanding of the participants' perceptions, highlighting the deeper meanings and relationships within the data and providing a comprehensive view of teaching practices tailored to meet the needs of diverse learners. The findings contribute to a broader understanding of inclusive education and emphasize the importance of targeted support and resources to enhance teaching effectiveness in this specialized field.

Table 1. Challenges and Difficulties Face by Teacher Teaching Physical Education to Special Children

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Had Limited Resources	No suitable lessons in books or online resources, I force myself to develop a strategy where it can be beneficial to the child. -IDI-01 Since I gave to them tasks there are resources that cannot get along to the tasks so that I used google to search more strategy to give the needs of my children. -IDI-02 The challenges arise due to the need for additional time, resources, and support. -IDI-03 In teaching students with cerebral palsy it is very challenging to choose resources, adapted equipment, and visual aids, to meet the needs of my students' progress. -IDI-04
Prepared Materials Based in Needs	I prepare various materials and lessons tailored to each child, with one lesson and set of materials for one child, and another lesson and set of materials for another child. -IDI-01 Things that I need to prepare for my students are the materials that are needed in teaching. -IDI-02 One notable struggle is to ensure that Instructional Materials and Methods are accessible and accommodating to each student's individual needs. -IDI-03 Teaching students with disabilities and teaching students without disabilities is a permanent struggle. Choosing Instructional Materials is a struggle though because I teach students with disabilities and without. -IDI-04 Choosing materials often becomes challenging when I experience struggles, especially when it deviate from what is typically expected of children. -IDI-05 Materials required for teaching children because not all are the same and needed by the child. As a teacher, you need to prepare a variety of materials to meet the individual needs of children. -IDI-06
Employed Differentiated Instruction and Materials	So, I modify everything when it comes to giving activities and, assisting in developing materials for the special needs of children. -IDI-01 What I provide them with are modified tasks in physical education as well to meet the needs of my students. -IDI-02 You also have to prepare activities that are suited for the learners because each learner has different abilities. So, you have to prepare different activities for different children. -IDI-05 The things that I need to prepare are my behavior as a teacher, especially when teaching students with disabilities like autism, due to the lengthy process involved. The curriculum must be modified by the teacher to suit the needs of the children. Accommodation refers to the materials provided, as we may need to consider that they may not be able to write because of their fine motor skills delay. So, the teacher will provide pictures to use as an exchange communication system, which is one of the things that teachers need to prepare. -IDI-06
Provided Guidance to Learners	I demonstrate the activity in front of them slowly and guide their feet and hands physically as they act so they can follow what you teach them. -IDI-01 I need to be able to demonstrate them to the child because once you demonstrate, they can work and get what I demonstrate to them so that they can follow along. -IDI-02 I always felt challenged every time I teach them because there is a process in teaching with them like in giving activity especially, especially in the instructions. -IDI-05 I am being challenged in teaching them because teaching students with disabilities requires step-by-step instruction, especially in activities. -IDI-06

Had Limited Resources

The study delves into the experiences of special needs unit teachers implementing a revised physical education curriculum, uncovering numerous challenges they face in the field. The participants' responses reveal a consistent struggle with limited resources, particularly the absence of specialized materials, textbooks, and tailored syllabuses essential for effective teaching. This scarcity not only hinders individual educators but also raises broader concerns about institutional support and resource allocation in special education. Furthermore, the study highlights a lack of specialized instructors and adapted resources, which places additional strain on teachers working to accommodate diverse learning needs. Despite these significant obstacles, the findings indicate that teachers are dedicated

to employing creative strategies and adapting available materials to provide meaningful instruction for special learners. These insights underscore the pressing need for enhanced resources and institutional support to empower educators in delivering high-quality, inclusive physical education (Banda, 2023).

Prepared Materials Based in Needs

The study captures the complex challenges special education teachers face in delivering an inclusive and effective learning experience, particularly for students with unique communication and learning needs. According to participant responses, these educators encounter persistent obstacles, such as limited access to authentic and specialized teaching materials, which are crucial for engaging and motivating special learners. As the literature highlights, the availability of appropriate resources plays a significant role in fostering student interest, especially for those with learning differences. However, teachers report struggling with a lack of materials and adapted resources, which undermines their efforts to create a supportive learning environment (Nyimbili, 2021). Additionally, the shortage of instructors proficient in sign language, combined with students' unfamiliarity with standard sign language, further complicates instruction. Teachers noted that reliance on both sign and verbal language can be time-intensive, and issues with interpreters sometimes result in students missing essential information (Banda, 2019). Despite these numerous challenges, educators demonstrate resilience, employing creative strategies to bridge communication gaps and adapt resources. These insights emphasize the critical need for institutional support and investment in specialized materials and training to improve the quality of education for all learners.

Employed Differentiated Instruction and Materials

The study sheds light on the experiences of teachers who implement differentiated instruction to address the unique needs of special learners, as revealed through participant responses. Teachers reported that the standard resources provided were often inadequate, prompting them to modify or adapt materials continually to fit the diverse needs of their students. This process, while essential for effective teaching, posed significant challenges, as it was both labor-intensive and time-consuming. The findings highlight the dedication of these educators, who invest substantial effort into customizing lessons to ensure inclusivity and engagement. However, the challenges associated with these modifications underscore the need for a shift in institutional perspectives toward more robust support and provision of resources tailored to diverse learners (Matafwali et al., 2020). These insights call for systemic changes to equip educators better and streamline the differentiation process, ultimately enhancing the educational experience for all students.

Provided Guidance to Learners

The study highlights the essential role of guidance and counseling teachers, as described by participants who shared their experiences working closely with students to foster personal and academic growth. Teachers emphasized that effective guidance and counseling require a proactive approach to problem-solving, aimed at helping students build self-confidence and achieve meaningful learning outcomes. This role is especially significant for supporting students in understanding their strengths and capabilities, which in turn enhances their educational performance (Harita, 2022). Additionally, participants acknowledged the foundational influence of parents in shaping children’s development from an early age, as parents are the first to impart knowledge, values, and interests, laying the groundwork for future learning and growth (Ruli, 2020). These insights underscore the collaborative nature of guidance and counseling, where both educators and parents play integral roles in supporting students' overall development.

Table 2. Cope with the difficulties they have experienced in teaching physical education to special children

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Creating an Inclusive Learning Environment	I did not limit their environment. They must interact with others, just like regular students. I allow them to showcase their potential skills and actively participate. -IDI-01 I allow my students to interact with their classmates to have communication and have a peer, along with physical prompting. This is one of the ways to demonstrate support for inclusive education. -IDI-02 I encourage peer support and inclusion by pairing special learners with classmates who can provide assistance, encouragement, and friendship during activities. -IDI-03 So, how do we support them and provide an environment that is suitable for them is well, if we talk about support, just calling the child over to join us here already means you are supporting their needs and what they should do. -IDI-04 So, allow them to play with other kids and their peers; do not exclude them. Some children may be introverted and may not like interacting with other kids, especially children with autism who may prefer solitude and dislike noise. Gradually, consider letting them spend a little time with others, perhaps by seating them in a different section, until they become comfortable and can integrate into a larger class setting. -IDI-05
Exploring Different Learning Strategies	I need to learn more strategies in teaching students with disabilities in my classroom and I also know the program I provide so that I can truly fit in and become an effective teacher. -IDI-01 I need to learn teaching strategies, especially since Down syndrome requires focus. Because you cannot meet their needs if you do not understand them, so what I did was I assessed them in a way where we all assessed the child. -IDI-02 Using differentiated instruction modified instructional materials, activities, and assessment. Utilized various teaching methods such as visual aids, hands-on activities, and technology. -IDI-03 I teach diligently I search various instructional materials so that I can meet their needs because if I just leave them be and observe them while I sit, without doing anything for them, I would not be able to meet their need. -IDI-04

Assessing and Supporting Learners	<p>You should play along with the kids and immerse yourself in their world so you can understand you need to adjust to their level and use strategies that suit their abilities. -IDI-05</p> <p>To teachers' daily experiences in teaching children, especially now with the implementation of inclusive education, teachers need to employ various strategies due to the diverse needs of children. -IDI-06</p> <p>The support that I need in teaching students with disabilities is from parents and co-teachers to have a partnership with them in teaching students with disabilities. -IDI-03</p> <p>We teach with the support of the department and support the parents because they are our partners in providing activities for the children. Even if it is cerebral palsy, they still have value. -IDI-04</p> <p>The teacher will conduct an assessment because, through pre-assessment, the teacher can see the needs and weaknesses of the child. -IDI-05</p> <p>I hope that with the partnership of co-teachers to meet the needs of the child, they will plan for an individual educational plan to target the needs of students. -IDI-06</p>
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Creating an Inclusive Learning Environment

In response, teachers play a crucial role in fostering an environment that accommodates the diverse needs of their students. They must adapt teaching strategies, utilize creative resources, and work collaboratively to ensure that all students feel included and supported. By embracing these challenges, teachers not only enhance their students' learning experiences but also contribute to a more inclusive school culture that celebrates diversity and promotes social growth. Creating an inclusive learning environment for children with special needs presents both challenges and opportunities for physical education teachers. These educators often face obstacles such as limited access to specialized teaching materials, the slow pace at which some students learn, a shortage of teachers trained in sign language, and varying levels of familiarity with standard sign language among students. However, the presence of inclusive classrooms allows students with special needs to benefit from socializing with their peers, who can model appropriate social interactions and encourage active engagement (Banda, 2019).

Exploring Different Learning Strategies

In response, educators working with special needs students can use such methods to actively involve all students, creating an inclusive and engaging environment that fosters growth, understanding, and participation for each learner. Teaching physical education to children with special needs requires a diverse set of strategies to accommodate unique learning requirements and enhance engagement. Research by Mwanza (2020) underscores the challenges faced by physical education teachers, including limited teaching materials and a lack of specialized knowledge in implementing certain methodologies. Studies, such as those by Tongwa et al. (2019) and Jothula et al. (2018), emphasize the importance of active learning techniques, particularly the demonstration method, as an effective strategy.

Assessing and Supporting Learners

As Warif (2019) notes, active involvement from both teachers and parents is essential to ensure that children with special needs receive the targeted support and encouragement they require to thrive academically and socially. Supporting the educational journey of children with special needs, including slow learners, requires a collaborative effort between teachers and parents. Teachers play a pivotal role in assessing individual learning needs and designing effective programs that utilize appropriate materials and tailored teaching methods to facilitate meaningful learning experiences. This partnership with parents is crucial, as it fosters a supportive environment that enhances the educational outcomes and overall development of each child.

Table 3. *The Insights that will be used in Teaching Approaches and Methodology for Special Children*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Be Knowledgeable and Resourceful	<p>Knowledge and skills are essential in teaching and with knowledge, and skills, it is much easier to become an effective teacher or instructor for them because if you have skills, you can easily devise strategies. -IDI-01</p> <p>As a teacher, you must master or be knowledgeable about the tasks before teaching them to the child because that is essential in teaching skills. -IDI-02</p> <p>Modification and adaptations in modified tasks, activities, and equipment to accommodate learners' individual needs, abilities, and interests. -IDI-03</p> <p>If we talk about teaching approaches and methodologies, in teaching students with disabilities as a teacher I used modified tasks for the learner with or without disabilities. -IDI-04</p>
Envelop the Atmosphere with Positivity	<p>The one that I consider an essential teaching skill is positive behavior management, employing this behavior strategy to create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment, fostering positive relationships, and addressing challenging behaviors effectively. -IDI-03</p> <p>What I consider essential teaching skills for me are my love and having good behavior for my children with disabilities. I consider them essential teaching skills, ones that I learned right in front of the children, where I saw my teaching skills during my time teaching the children. I learned them during the time I spent with the children. I would search for skills that can address the needs of the child deeply. -IDI-04</p> <p>When it comes to teaching children with autism, let us just say that for all types of disabilities, as a teacher I need to adopt a strategy that can be suited to the needs of my children. -IDI-05</p> <p>As a teacher you must equip the teaching skills, strategies, and methodologies to apply the needs of students with disabilities. -IDI-06</p>

Be Knowledgeable and Resourceful

After retrieving and analyzing the data gathered from the participants, Teachers teaching children with special needs requires educators to be both knowledgeable and resourceful, especially in adapting content to meet diverse learning needs. Special education teachers must possess a deep understanding of subject matter and be equipped to address challenges through innovative problem-solving and creative use of available resources. According to David et al. (2020), general educators should also make well-informed decisions grounded in thorough assessments, foster empathy and understanding, and prioritize effective communication within and beyond the classroom. By embodying these qualities, teachers can create an inclusive, supportive, and adaptive learning environment that meets the unique needs of each student.

Envelop the Atmosphere with Positivity

By promoting positivity, teachers play a vital role in nurturing resilience, growth, and well-being in children with special needs. Creating a positive atmosphere is essential for teaching children with special needs, as it fosters a supportive and encouraging learning environment. Teachers who approach their work with optimism and a hopeful attitude can inspire and uplift their students, helping them feel more engaged and confident. This positive energy not only benefits students but also influences those around them, creating a ripple effect that extends to families, communities, and beyond. As noted by Rahman (2022) and Carmels et al. (2021), a holistic approach to child protection—supported by parents, communities, and governing bodies—is crucial in ensuring that children's rights are upheld and that protective measures are effectively implemented.

Conclusions

In conclusion, when teaching physical education to special children, educators need to embody qualities such as knowledge, resourcefulness, consideration, and understanding. By being well-informed about the unique needs and abilities of each student, teachers can tailor their instruction to create inclusive and effective physical education experiences. Resourcefulness enables educators to adapt activities, equipment, and teaching methods to suit diverse learners. Consideration and understanding cultivate a supportive and empathetic learning environment, promoting the holistic development of special children. By combining expertise, adaptability, empathy, and inclusivity, teachers can provide enriching and empowering physical education experiences that enhance the overall well-being and growth of special children.

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